

EFFECT OF EMPOWERMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION ON COMMITMENT OF PRIVATE MIDDLE SCHOOL TEACHER ORGANIZATIONS IN EAST KARAWANG

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study to 1) analyze the positive direct effect of empowerment on organizational commitment, 2) to analyze the positive direct effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment, and 3) to analyze the positive direct effect of empowerment on job satisfaction. This study uses survey method with causal techniques. Population in the study was private junior high school teachers in East Karawang which amounted to 108 people, with a sample of 85 people. The research data was collected by research instrument in the form of questionnaire. Data analysis about the influence of other variables using quantitative approach while to explain the influence between variables using path analysis. The data collected were analyzed using path analysis (path analysis). The result of this research conclude that 1) empowerment have positive direct effect to organizational commitment, 2) job satisfaction have positive direct effect to organizational commitment, and 3) empowerment have positive direct effect to job satisfaction.*

Keywords: *Empowerment, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment*

INTRODUCTION

Organizational commitment has become a strategic issue lately because the world of education has been placed in a decent and strategic position. Improving teacher welfare through certification programs or performance benefits that will roll over the next few years is a challenge for a teacher's professional commitment. The question is then, is a teacher still commenting on his profession and organization when the material welfare or finances are getting better. Questions about the commitment of the teacher's organization will continue to see the reality of the teacher's life which tends to be far from the expectations of society.

Various problems in building education and culture that need attention in the next five years are explained in general in the Ministry of Education and Culture strategic plan (2015-2019) where the teacher absence rate is higher in (i) male teachers, (ii) teachers who teach more than one school, (iii) teachers who teach in remote schools, (iv) schools

that have insufficient facilities and infrastructure, (v) schools that have not reached SPM, (vi) principals who are often absent and do not become role models , (vii) schools that were rarely visited by the district education office, and (viii) schools with less active school committees.

Teachers as education personnel are one of the determining factors for the success of educational goals because teachers are directly connected with students to provide guidance that will produce *output* the expected. Teachers are required to have a high commitment to schools in order to realize the goals of the organization and the goals of national education in accordance with the law. Commitment is defined as the level of trust and acceptance of employees towards the goals of the organization and has the desire to remain in the organization.

Studies show that high levels of organizational commitment are associated with low levels of absenteeism and *turnover*, this can be used as a basis for doing an action (Dee *et al.*2002: 95). Agreeing with this, according to Robbins and Judge (2011: 77), "*organizational commitment is the degree to wich an employee identifies with a particular organization and its goals and goals to maintain membership in the organization*". A teacher is required to have high organizational commitment because as an educator it is natural to provide the best for his school for the sake of his dedication to creating a quality generation. In addition, so that the teacher's commitment can be carried out properly requires effective guidance and empowerment of the principal in empowering the potential members of the organization so that the vision and mission can be achieved.

Based on the previous description and seeing the phenomenon of school conditions in East Karawang based on several writings and interviews conducted shows that the commitment of private junior high school teacher organizations in East Karawang is still not optimal, this is due to many factors. Among them is the factor of low job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a health condition for someone who feels positive things in their organization. The more positive one's feelings result in the higher organizational commitment. In addition to indications of low job satisfaction, teachers feel less empowered. The teacher feels that the principal does not believe in his potential so that there is a lack of motivation to be actively involved in an activity. This can be seen from giving responsibility only to certain teachers and not giving the opportunity to others to get involved. In addition, decision making by the teacher must also require approval from the principal so that the work becomes delayed and cannot be completed quickly. Organizational commitment that grows in schools is driven by leaders who are able to empower the values of kindness, honesty, morale, innovation, to the behavior of their subordinate organizations.

Teachers who have a high commitment to the organization can certainly improve the quality of education, especially in private junior high schools in the East Karawang region so that schools can continue to grow. Several previous studies have shown the importance of organizations having highly committed employees. Azeem's research (2010) states that the success of an organization in pursuing quality does not only depend on how the organization develops the competence of its employees, but also on how the organization increases the commitment of its employees, both the commitment to work and the direction of superiors. Yavuz (2010) argues that organizational commitment is one of the main activities and one of the main objectives in the organization's efforts to maintain its existence. Safitri (2014) states an organization, whatever its form requires a

high commitment from all its members so that organizational and individual goals can be achieved. Tania and Eddy (2013) suggest that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the organizational commitment. This is supported by the results of research conducted by Wilanda (2013) which shows that there is a significant influence of job satisfaction with organizational commitment. Sunarno and Lie (2015) stated that teacher's organizational commitment in a school or educational institution can be a force to run a school program. The high commitment of teachers to schools will facilitate the achievement of school goals. Teacher job satisfaction is very important because it contributes to the success of the school, among others, can increase productivity with quality education processes and services, and can also reduce absenteeism. In addition, teacher job satisfaction is very important because it can increase teacher's organizational commitment in school and work performance.

Organizational Commitment Organizational

commitment according to Mowday, Steers, and Porter as quoted by Colquit, LePine, and Wesson (2009: 67) that, "*organizational commitment as the desire on the part of an employee to remain a member of the organization.*" Organizational commitment is the activity of employees to remain members of an organization. This commitment to the organization will influence whether the employee remains an organizational member (*is retained*) or leaves the organization to find another job (*turns over*).

According to Steven L. Mc. Shane and Mary Ann Von Glinow (2008: 119), "*organizational commitment refers to an employee's emotional attachment to identification with, and involvement in a particular organization.*" Organizational commitment refers to the attachment of emotional employees, identification with, and involvement in certain organizations.

The definition and nature of the commitment at this time is no longer merely in the form of an individual's willingness to stay in an institution or organization for a long time. But more than that, members of the organization are willing to give the best to the organization even willing to offer something beyond the limits required by the organization. This of course can only happen if employees feel happy and satisfied in the organization concerned. Like the opinion of Luthans (2008: 147), "*As an attitude, organizational commitment is most often defined as (1) a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization; (2) a willingness to exert high level of effort on behalf of the organization; and (3) a definite belief in, and acceptance of the values and goals the organization.*"

Organizational commitment as an attitude, organizational commitment is most often defined as (1) a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization; (2) the desire to mobilize a high level of business on behalf of the organization; and (3) certainly trust, and acceptance, values and goals of the organization.

In the opinion of McShane and Von Glinow (2008: 356) that, "*the strong commitment of influenza, where by people identify with the influencer's request and are highly motivated to implement it even when extrinsic sources of motivation are no longer present.*" Commitment is the most influential force by people who identify, give influence and high motivation to carry out commitments and become the most important source of longer motivation.

Based on the review of the concepts above, it can be synthesized that organizational commitment in this study is an emotional bond of a person who is strong towards the organization so that they are able to work voluntarily, want to maintain membership and constantly participate actively in the organization to achieve organizational goals, with indicators: (1) alignment with organizational goals, (2) fully involved in organizational tasks, (3) loyal to the organization.

Empowerment.

John Schermerhorn *et.al*(2011: 289) means "*empowerment is the process by which managers help others to acquire and use the power needed to make decisions affect themselves and their work*". The concept above states that empowerment means that a manager gives breadth to employees so that they are able to work independently to complete their tasks.

Empowerment according to Jennifer M. George and Garteh R. Jones (2012: 25), "*empowerment is the process of giving employees the authority to make important decisions and to be responsible for their outcomes*". Freely, employee empowerment is one of the efforts and strategies to provide opportunities for employees and be responsible for their performance. Empowered teachers have a competitive advantage. Therefore, various strategies are needed to develop and renew the ability and expertise of teachers in dealing with various problems in the world of education.

Whereas Nancy Langton and Stephen P. Robbins (2007: 412) explained that, "*empowerment refers to tea freedom and ability of employees to make decisions and commitments*". Empowerment leads to the freedom and ability of employees in making decisions, as well as in carrying out work commitments.

Empowerment will make someone feel important, happy and challenged by their work, and is part of a team. The same thing was expressed by Fred Luthans (2008: 290), "*empowerment is the authority to make decisions within one's area of responsibility with the first having to get approval from someone else*". Empowerment is the granting of authority to give decisions in the scope of one's responsibility without waiting for the approval of others.

Although empowerment is similar to traditional delegated authority, there are two characteristics, namely: (1) *that employees are encouraged to use their own initiative*. Employees are encouraged to use their own initiative, and (2) *employees are given not only the authority but also the resources, so they are able to make decisions and have the power to get them implemented*. Empowered employees are not only authorized, but also use resources to implement them.

Based on the review of the concepts that have been described previously, it can be synthesized that empowerment is the giving of authority and responsibility of the leadership to employees to carry out tasks creatively and innovatively in responding to various dynamic changes according to their capabilities with indicators: 1) giving responsibility or authority according to expertise, 2) involvement in decision making, and 3) giving opportunities to develop themselves.

Job satisfaction

John R. Schermerhorn (2011: 347) defines job satisfaction, "*job satisfaction is the degree to which an individual feels positive or negative about a job*". Job satisfaction is the extent to which a person feels positive or negative about work.

According to Jason A. Colquitt, Jeffery A. Lepine, Michael J. Wesson (2015: 98), *Job satisfaction is defined as an emotional state that results in the form of the appraisal of one's job on job experiences. In the word, it represents how you feel about your job and what you think about jobs.* Job satisfaction is defined as emotions or feelings of pleasure or not towards the results of an assessment of a job and work experience. And can describe how you feel about work and what you think about the job.

In line with that, Robert Kreithner, Angelo Kinicki (2011: 170), "*job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response toward various facets of one's job*". Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects of one's work.

Furthermore, James L. Gibson, John M. Ivancevich, James H. Donnelly and Robert Konopaske (2012: 104) define the work requirements, *Job satisfaction is that individuals have about their jobs. It results from their perception of their jobs, based on factors of the work environment, work group affiliation, working conditions and fringe benefits.* Job satisfaction is someone's attitude about his job. This is as a result of the perception of his work which is based on work environment factors, job security, working conditions and income.

While Laurie J. Mullins (2010: 701) defines that *Job satisfaction is it self a complex concept and difficult to measure objectively. The level of job satisfaction is related to individual, social, cultural, organizational, and environmental factors.* Job satisfaction itself is a concept that is complex and difficult to measure objectively. Job satisfaction levels are influenced by various variables related to individuals, social, cultural, organizational and environmental factors. Teacher job satisfaction is very important indeed. This is because it relates to several aspects of learning. Even the views of some experts on job satisfaction are Jennifer M. George and Gareth R. Jones (2012: 71), "*job satisfaction is having their own jobs*". Satisfaction is a collection of one's feelings and beliefs about their current work. In an organization a teacher must have a level of satisfaction in work. Thus job satisfaction must be obtained by every teacher or even a teacher in their respective work environments.

Based on several notions of job satisfaction above, it can be synthesized that job satisfaction is a pleasant or positive response to one's feelings resulting from the assessment of one's work or work experience, with indicators: (1) feeling towards work results, (2) feelings for appreciation in work, (3) feelings for the work environment, (4) feelings for self-development opportunities, and (5) feelings for colleagues.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted in private junior high schools in East Karawang. The method used in this study is a survey method with causal techniques. Affordable population in this study private junior high school teachers in East Karawang totaling 108 teachers, with a sample of 85, the data in this study were collected through questionnaires in the form of *rating scale* with a score distribution between 1 to 5. After descriptive analysis continued with analysis requirements test in the form of analysis requirements

analysis in the form of normality test, data linearity test and regression significance, hypothesis testing is done using path analysis techniques .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Empowerment Effect on Organizational Commitment

From the results of testing the first hypothesis it can be concluded that there is a positive direct effect of Empowerment on Organizational Commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.410 and a path coefficient of 0.307. This gives the meaning of Empowerment has a direct positive effect on Organizational Commitment.

The results of this study are in line with the opinions of several experts including Stephen P. Robbins and Timothy A. Judge (2007: 102) said through empowerment in increasing the parity and members and will have an impact on increasing organizational commitment, *"pshycological empowerment of employees' belief in the degree to which they affect their work, environment, their competence, the meaningfulness of their jobs and their perceived autonomy in their works. With their confidence, they can estimate the extent to which they can influence the work environment, competence, meaningfulness in work and the perceived freedom of work.*

Another thing was emphasized by Andrian Furnham (2011: 76), that empowerment requires authority and responsibility, this means that the teacher needs to be given authority to make decisions if they feel right, there is control in work, is ready to accept risks and learn from every mistake made, *" empowerment is essentially the process that attempts to give employees more autonomy at work"*. Based on this statement it is clear that empowerment requires the commitment of teachers to have high loyalty, ready to be involved in carrying out tasks on the basis of skills, expertise, and responsibility so that it really needs to be committed.

In line with this, Nancy Langton and Stephen P. Robbins (2007: 298), define *"empowerment to the freedom of ability and employees of make decisions and commitments"*. Empowerment leads to freedom and ability in making decisions, as well as in upholding commitments. Based on the theory above, that empowerment is related to an employee's commitment. Commitments based on the obligations of the profession chosen by a teacher are not just part of the institution of education or school. Empowered teachers will be willing to give high commitment to improve the achievement of school vision. With this commitment, as written by Laurie J. Mullins (2005: 902) namely through the three pillars of commitment

- 1) *A sense of belonging to the organization; as a basis for building loyalty, such as: informed, onvolved, sharing in success.*
- 2) *A sense of excitement in job; feeling happy working because of the motivation manifested in: pride, trust, accountability for result.*
- 3) *Confidence in management; believe in organizational management because feelings are valued by the leader shown in: authority, dedication, competence.*

One of the implications of the above description is that if empowered the teacher will have a high commitment as a tool to assess the teacher's responsibility to the school. Based on the theory above, there is a positive direct influence on empowerment of commitment.

Effect of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment

From the results of testing the third hypothesis it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.387 and a path coefficient of 0.269. This gives the meaning of Job Satisfaction has a direct positive effect on Organizational Commitment.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion of some experts including Colquitt, LePine and Wesson (2011: 105) stating that, "*job satisfaction is one of several individual mechanisms that directly effect job performance and organization commitment*". Job satisfaction is the behavior of several individuals who directly influence work performance and organizational commitment. This means that if employees feel a high level of satisfaction with their work and have a positive emotional experience at work, they will provide the best work and choose to continue working for the organization for a long time.

Furthermore, Colquitt (2009: 125) revealed that, "*Job satisfaction has strong positive effect on organizational commitment. People who experience higher levels of job satisfaction tend to feel higher levels of affective commitment and higher levels of normative commitment. Effect on continuance commitment are weaker*". Job satisfaction has a strong positive effect. People who have more work experience and higher levels of satisfaction tend to have higher normative and attitudinal commitment. However, this results in a weak commitment. That is, the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the affective commitment and normative commitment.

Byars and Rue (1991: 303) stated, "*employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be committed to these organizations are likely to be very loyal and dependable*". Employees who are satisfied with their work tend to commit to the organization. The employee becomes very loyal and reliable.

Based on the description above, job satisfaction has a direct positive effect on organizational commitment, if job satisfaction is improved, it will lead to increased organizational commitment.

Empowerment Effect on Job Satisfaction

From the results of testing the second hypothesis it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence on Empowerment of Job Satisfaction with a correlation coefficient value of 0.384 and a path coefficient value of 0.384. This gives the meaning of empowerment has a direct positive effect on job satisfaction.

The results of this study are in line with the opinions of some experts, among them according to De Janazs (2009: 389), empowerment affects job satisfaction as follows, "*Empowerment participation and growth reinforcement members, commitment to quality, and a more open, honest environment. This results in greater job satisfaction, motivation, and commitment - a sense of achievement*". Empowering members will strengthen member participation and development, commitment to quality, an honest and more open environment. This causes an increase in job satisfaction, motivation and commitment.

Furthermore Fisk (2013: 252) stated that, "*Empowered employees are more satisfied with their jobs, have an increased sense of personal efficacy through participation in decision-making and are encouraged to set up skills and abilities to address different scenarios*". Empowered employees are more satisfied with their work,

have a sense of personal success through participation in decision making and are encouraged to utilize a range of skills and abilities to overcome different scenarios.

Furthermore Amir and Amien (2014: 13) stated that, "*When employees are empowered, their confidence degree and self reliance will increase. The extra confidence is a goddess thing because it creates job satisfaction and high levels of productivity.* When employees are empowered, the level of confidence and independence will increase. Extra trust is a good thing because it creates job satisfaction and a high level of productivity. In this case empowerment, the involvement of employees with the organization and fellow co-workers and awards will foster a feeling of satisfaction of the employee for his work. Employees are given greater autonomy in carrying out various tasks, functions and obligations, empowered their potential and motivated. Employees are encouraged to be more creative and innovative in their work, valued in their creativity aimed at the success of the organization. This situation increases job satisfaction. Based on the description above, empowerment has a direct positive effect on job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the calculation of research data and the results of the data analysis that has been described. then it can be obtained some conclusions as follows: 1) Empowerment directly affects organizational commitment. This means that this is shown by a strong desire to maintain himself as a teacher at the school. A strong will to mobilize its work effort and confidence to keep abreast of organizational rules and stated goals. Empowered teachers will be willing to give high commitment to improve the achievement of school vision. 2) Job satisfaction directly affects organizational commitment. This means that if members feel a high level of satisfaction with their work and have a positive emotional experience at work, they will provide the best work and choose to continue working for the organization for a long time. 3) Empowerment has a direct positive effect on interpersonal communication. That is, empowering members will strengthen member participation and development, commitment to quality, an honest and more open environment. This causes an increase in job satisfaction.

Suggestion: Based on the conclusions above the research suggested various efforts made in order to increase the commitment of private junior high school teacher organizations in East Karawang. To the principal to be able to pay attention to the teacher and encourage teachers to maintain a level of confidence and develop skills in work, build trust relationships between the principal and teacher, facilitate teachers to develop their potential by providing rewards for teachers who have high achievement and dedication. As well as providing opportunities for teachers to attend education and training. For teachers increasing the organizational commitment of teachers by fostering a sense of loyalty to the school where teaching and love and pride in the work is teaching in school. For other researchers, so that this research can be generalized more broadly and refined can further broaden generalizations about the scope of the study and the range of populations.

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